

Effect of Extreme Photoperiodic Condition-constant Dark and Melatonin Pretreatment on Ampicillin induced Nephrotoxicity in Wild Tropical Rodent, Indian palm squirrel, *F. pennanti*.

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Running Title: Nephrotoxicity by Ampicilline sodium

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Introduction:

From the previous studies, it is quite evident that Ampicillin sodium at a lower dose (40mg/Kg body wt) in wild tropical rodent *Funambulus pennanti* produces nephrotoxicity by increasing free radical load. This toxicity is limited by pretreatment of melatonin with physiological dose (250µg/kg body wt) in *Rattus norvegicus* and at higher doses (500µg/kg body wt) in *Funambulus pennanti*. Recent work indicated that constant light suppressed hydroxyindole-O-methyltransferase (HIOMT) activity and constant dark increased it (Arendt, 1995) when HIOMT does not show a definite rhythm in 24 hour light/dark cycle. Further, circadian rhythms in general which are well defined in light-dark cycles persist or free run under CD conditions and are suppressed by constant light (Binkley, 1993). In the night at about 2am to 3am is the point when melatonin reaches its peak, and probably due to the increased concentration of melatonin, lipid peroxidation is reduced. Thus, melatonin decreases lipid peroxidation directly and indirectly by stimulating GSH-Px activity. Belanger et al. (1991) reported that the minimal lipid peroxidation level in rat liver tissue was at 01:00 h which the appropriate peak time of melatonin. It may be the increase in melatonin secretion during night responsible for, at least in part, for the nocturnal elevation of total antioxidative status and for the reduction of lipid peroxidation observed in Indian palm squirrel.

Considering these data in relation to melatonin and antioxidant systems in kidney, (Pierrefiche and Laborit, 1995) under-took the present research. The main aim was to evaluate the exogenous effects of melatonin and constant dark exposure on antioxidant enzyme activities in renal tissue (TAS% and SOD), oxidative stress lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) with biochemical parameters like acid phosphatase (ACP), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), creatinine and urea in both blood (BUN) and urine to access the functional status of kidney and as a whole the organism.

Materials and Methods:

Thirty five (35) adult male squirrels (weighing 100g to 120g each) were used in this study. The squirrels were collected in the month of February from the vicinity of the Varanasi (Lat. 25°18'N; Long. 83°01'E) and acclimatized for two weeks in a room fully exposed to

ambient environmental conditions (Light 12.50 hr; Temp. 20–25°C; Humidity, 29–50%). The animals were housed in wire net cages (25" X 75" X 30") and had an access to food consisting of soaked gram seeds (*Cicer arietinum*) and water ad libitum. Later, the squirrels were divided into five groups of seven animals each.

Group-I Control.

Seven male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above without any treatment (NDL).

Group-II Continuous dark Control (DD; 24 h dark: 0h light).

Seven male squirrels were kept under constant dark conditions as mentioned in materials and methods, with no treatment as constant dark control (DD).

Group-III Continuous dark (DD; 24 h dark: 0h light) with Melatonin.

Seven male squirrels were kept under constant dark conditions as mentioned in materials and methods, with exogenous dose of Melatonin (500µg/kg body weight per day every evening between 5:30 pm to 6:30 pm) prepared fresh every day in saline, was injected subcutaneously under red light condition (DD+Mel).

Group-IV Continuous dark (DD; 24 h dark: 0h light) with Ampicillin Sodium.

Seven male squirrels were kept under constant dark conditions as mentioned in materials and methods, with single dose of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body weight per day every morning between 10am to 11am) reconstituted fresh every day (DD+Amp).

Group-V Continuous dark (DD; 24 dark: 0h light) with Ampicillin and Melatonin.

Seven male squirrels were kept under constant dark conditions as mentioned in materials and methods. Animals were treated with a single intra-venous dose of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body weight per day every morning between 10am to 11am) reconstituted fresh every day and melatonin (500µg/kg body weight/day) in the evening hours between 5:30 pm to 6:30 pm, prepared fresh every third day in saline, was injected subcutaneously under constant dark condition. (DD+Amp+Mel). All the treatments were given for seven days and on the eighth day after 24 hours of last treatments animals were decapitated. Trunk blood was collected in separate centrifuge tubes and serum was taken for biochemical estimations.

Sample collection:

The treatment was given for total seven days (i.e. total seven melatonin injection and seven plus seven melatonin followed by ampicillin injection). On eighth day i.e. after 24 hours of last treatment squirrels were sacrificed by decapitation after complete ether anesthesia. The urinary bladder was surgically extruded and emptied in a sterile tube by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured collection of urine produced over a period of 60 min. Kidney tissues were also fixed in Bouin's fluid for histology. The experiment and handling of animals were performed in accordance with institutional practice and within the framework of revised Animal (Scientific Procedures) Act of 2003 and 2007 of Govt. of India on animal welfare.

Parameters Assayed:

All the treatments were given for seven days and on the eighth day that is after 24 hours of last treatments animals were decapitated. The bladder was surgically extruded and emptied by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured collection of urine produced over a period of 60 min. At the time of sacrifice, thus urine was collected, and its volume was measured and biochemical parameters ACP, ALP, Creatinine and Urea were estimated. After removal of both kidneys through a midline abdominal incision, the right and left kidneys were processed. The kidneys were stripped from their capsule, weighed, and slit open by longitudinal incision. Cortical, medullary (outer medulla), and papillary (inner medulla-papillary tip) components were separated under a dissecting microscope. The accuracy of the dissection was verified by light microscopy.

Renal cortical tissue homogenates were prepared separately (as mentioned in materials and methods) for the detection of Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD), lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) and Total antioxidative status (TAS %). Trunk Blood was collected in separate centrifuge tubes and blood/plasma was taken for biochemical estimations that are BUN, ACP, ALP, creatinine and Total kidney cortical protein.

Histology:

After fixation in Bouin’s fluid for 22 hours, kidney was paraffin embedded and cut into 6-µm sections. Deparaffinized sections were stained using hematoxylin and eosin. Kidney morphology was observed under microscope (Leica MPV-3, Germany). The morphometric analysis of capsular space and cellular integrity (PCT, DCT & glomerulus) of kidney cortical region were done in 20 serial sections randomly selected from each animal with the help of filar ocular micrometer (Webcon Pvt. Ltd. India).

Statistical analysis:

All the data were expressed as means ± SEM of at least five animals per group. Data comparisons were statistically analyzed by using ANOVA followed by Student Newman-Keuls’ multiple range tests. The differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$ (Bruning and Knitz, 1977). Microsoft Excel program was used for statistical calculations.

Results:

Fig. 1

Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant dark (DD) condition on Acid phosphatase (ACP) in (A) blood, (B) urine and alkaline phosphatase (ALP)

in (C) blood, (D) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.001$. Control (Control) vs Constant dark (DD), Constant dark + Ampicillin treated (DD + Amp), Constant dark + Melatonin treated (DD + mel) and Constant dark + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (DD + mel + ampi) groups.

Fig. 2

Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500 μ g/Kg body wt) under constant dark (DD) condition on blood urea nitrogen (BUN) (A), urine urea (B) and creatinine in blood (C) urine (D) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.001$. Control (Control) vs Constant dark (DD), Constant dark + Ampicillin treated (DD + Amp), Constant dark + Melatonin treated (DD + mel) and Constant dark + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (DD + mel + ampi) groups.

Fig. 3

(A) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant dark (DD) condition on the malon-dialdehyde level (TBARS) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.001. Control (Control) vs Constant dark (DD), Constant dark + Ampicillin treated (DD + Amp), Constant dark + Melatonin treated (DD + mel) and Constant dark + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (DD + mel + ampi) groups.

(B) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant dark (DD) condition on the total kidney cortical protein weight of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.001. Control (Control) vs Constant dark (DD), Constant dark + Ampicillin treated (DD + Amp), Constant dark + Melatonin treated (DD + mel) and Constant dark + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (DD + mel + ampi) groups.

(C) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant dark (DD) condition on super oxide-dismutase activity (SOD) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference * p<0.05 and ** p<0.001. Control (Control) vs Constant dark (DD), Constant dark + Ampicillin treated (DD + Amp), Constant dark + Melatonin treated (DD + mel) and Constant dark + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (DD + mel + ampi) groups.

(D) Effect of melatonin pretreatment (500µg/Kg body wt) under constant dark (DD) condition on the total antioxidative status (TAS %) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM, (N=7); Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of

difference ** $p < 0.001$. Control (Control) vs Constant dark (DD), Constant dark + Ampicillin treated (DD + Amp), Constant dark + Melatonin treated (DD + mel) and Constant dark + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (DD + mel + ampi) groups.

Plate 1

Histomicrograph of squirrel kidney cortical region showing Glomerulus (G), increased capsular space (→), affected brush bordered vesicular epithelial cells (BBVEC) (*) of proximal convoluted tubule (PCT), distal convoluted tubule (DCT), loop of henle and collecting tubule. (Under 40X objective)

- A- Control (Control)
- B- Constant dark (DD)
- C- Constant dark + Ampicillin treated (DD + Amp)
- D- Constant dark + Melatonin treated (DD + mel)
- E- Constant dark + Melatonin + Ampicillin treated (DD + mel + ampi)

Exposure of squirrels to constant dark with nephropathy induced by Ampicillin, led to a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) and significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) was noted in total protein and in total antioxidative status (TAS%) and SOD enzyme activity in the kidney cortical tissues (Fig. 3). A significant ($p < 0.01$) increase was noted in acid & alkaline phosphatase, Creatinine, urea in blood and urine while significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease was noted in ACP in blood, urine, ALP in urine in melatonin treated groups in groups under DD condition (Fig. 1, 2). Continuous dark exposure had no effect on ACP, ALP and creatinine. There was significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in SOD activity but no significant change was noted in TAS %, TBARS and total kidney cortical protein under constant dark condition when compared to controls of normal day length. Pretreatment of exogenous dose of melatonin (500

µg/kg body wt.) to ampicillin treated groups caused a significant decrease ($p < 0.01$) in TBARS level. Combine treatment of melatonin and ampicillin prompted no significant change in TAS%. Moreover, antioxidant enzymes Superoxide dismutase registered increase in activity following melatonin administration both in the ampicillin and DD group.

No significant change in capsular space and cellular integrity was noted in squirrels under DD and melatonin groups alone and in DD + Mel when compared with control group. Ampicillin under constant dark condition decreased capsular space significantly ($p < 0.01$) while DD + Mel + Amp group increased it and maintained cellular integrity of PCT (Plate 1 & Table 1).

3 Discussion:

Exposure to constant dark (DD) increased pineal melatonin in squirrel indicating the increased metabolic activity of the pineal gland (Shavali and Haldar, 1998). This may be because of the increased activity of pineal N-acetyl-transferase (NAT), the rate limiting enzyme in Mel production during dark. DD is most effective stimulator for pineal function and melatonin production than SP (Haldar et al., 1992) for this species of rodent. Similarly, in our study, lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) decreased during the dark period (Diaz-Munoz et al., 1985). Oxidative stress would have caused inflammation and fibrosis by direct toxic effects of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and by inducing activation of redox-sensitive pro-inflammatory transcription factors and signal transduction pathways this would have enhanced by the Ampicillin treatment for as a part of its antibacterial killing mechanism of action. Therefore, oxidative stress and its constant companion, inflammation, would have played a major role in the progression of renal injury (Rodriguez-Iturbe et al., 2001) as well as in the development of various complications of chronic renal failure. Oxidative stress in chronic kidney disease (CKD) is caused by a combination of excessive ROS production and antioxidant depletion. Significant up regulation of NAD(P)H oxidase, a main source of ROS, has been demonstrated in the remnant kidney and in cardiovascular tissues in the 5/6 nephrectomized rats (Vaziri et al., 2003), and spontaneous production of superoxide and hydrogen peroxide has been shown in circulating leukocytes of patients with end-stage kidney disease (Yoon et al., 2007).

In the present study, we found that Ampicillin treatment causes significant biochemical and structural changes as compared with control squirrels even under constant dark (DD) exposure but the damage in Ampicillin treated groups were further prevented by administration of exogenous melatonin pretreatment under constant dark. This protection was manifested by reduced lipid peroxidation level (TBARS), increased levels of TAS% and less damage as inferred by the biochemical and histological observation of kidney cortical regions. Total anti-oxidative status (TAS%) is related to melatonin levels (Reiter, 1992), thus the increase in melatonin in continuous dark could be a factor in decreased oxidative damage. This study shows that constant dark reduce levels of lipid peroxidation products and morphological damage and enhances the anti-oxidative defense system. Under normal conditions, excessive formation of free radicals and related damage at cellular and tissue levels is controlled by cellular anti-oxidant defense systems. These radicals may exceed the capacity of cellular intrinsic free radical-scavenging systems and induce cellular dysfunction and this is believed to be involved in the etiology of many diseases (Lefer and Granger, 2000; Butterfield et al., 2001). Aging in normal animals with an intact pineal gland is associated with increased oxidative damage accompanied by elevated lipid peroxidation products and morphological changes (Rai et al., 2009).

Melatonin is known to scavenge reactive oxygen species, such as hydroxyl radicals, superoxide anion radicals, singlet oxygen and peroxynitrite anions, and to induce anti-oxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione reductase, and

glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase under various conditions (Reiter et al., 1998, 2001; Reiter, 1998; Sharma & Haldar, 2008). Consequently, our data support the hypothesis that increased melatonin during continuous dark plays an important role in oxidative stress and may attenuate tissue injury caused by antibiotic Ampicillin due to oxidant stress.

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